

RESULTS BEFORE AND AFTER TREATMENT OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE WITH VARIOUS CONCOMITANT DISEASES

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Abstract: In most patients, especially the elderly, chronic heart failure is accompanied by a number of concomitant diseases that play an important role in its development and response to treatment. Comorbidity is defined as a chronic condition that coexists in a patient with another established disease. A distinction is made between non-cardiac pathological conditions and cardiac diseases that are directly related to the presence of chronic heart failure, such as arrhythmia, as well as conditions that precede and contribute to its development, such as arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus and hyperlipidemia. 120 patients with CHF in our observation were divided into three groups, the first group consisted of 40 patients with CHF II-III FS albuminuria and one comorbid disease. The second group consisted of 40 patients with CHF II-III FS albuminuria and two comorbid diseases.

The third group consisted of 40 patients diagnosed with CHF II-III FS albuminuria and three or more comorbid diseases. In all cases, CHF was caused by ischemic heart disease, postinfarction cardiosclerosis and arterial hypertension. In some cases, the anamnesis and objective examination revealed that ischemic heart disease and hypertension caused CHF in one patient simultaneously. All patients received a beta-blocker as a standard treatment for CHF, alzisartan as an angiotensin receptor blocker and epirenone, the latest generation mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist, as an antifibrotic agent. In some cases, cardiac glycosides, diuretics and antiarrhythmic agents were prescribed based on the instructions. Numerical analysis shows that it has a reliable ($R < 0.05$) positive effect on the clinical condition of patients. The analysis confirmed that the patients' resistance to physical activity, quality of life and clinical condition of the patients changed positively according to the number of comorbid conditions of CHF. Key words: comorbid conditions, cystatin-S, aldosterone, TGF- β 1.

Keywords: comorbid conditions, aldosterone, TGF- β 1, quality of life, treatment.

Materials and methods: 120 patients with CHF under our observation were divided into three groups. The first group consisted of 40 patients with CHF II-III FS albuminuria and one comorbid disease. Their average age was 58.3 ± 4.2 years, including 17 men and 23 women. The second group consisted of 40 patients with albuminuria CHF II-III FS diagnosed with two comorbid diseases, whose average age was 61.8 ± 4.7 years. The second group included 19 men and 21 women.

The third group consisted of 40 patients diagnosed with CHF II-III FS albuminuria and three or more comorbid diseases. Their average age was 65.9 ± 5.3 years, 21 men and 19 women. In all cases, CHF was caused by ischemic heart disease, postinfarction cardiosclerosis and arterial hypertension. In some cases, the anamnesis and objective examination revealed that ischemic heart disease and hypertension caused CHF in one patient simultaneously. The amount of proteins lost per day in the first group of patients was 335.6 mg/l, in the second group - 499.9 mg/l, in the third group - 614.4 mg/l. The indicators before and after

treatment were also compared. All patients received a beta blocker as standard treatment for CHF, alisartan as an angiotensin receptor blocker, and epi renone, a latest-generation mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist, as an antifibrotic agent. Based on the instructions, cardiac glycosides, diuretics, and antiarrhythmic agents were prescribed in individual cases.

DATA ON COMORBID DISEASES IDENTIFIED IN PATIENTS ENROLLED IN THE STUDY

№	Groups	Patients with chronic heart failure II-III FS with albuminuria and one concomitant disease n=40		Patients with chronic heart failure II-III FS with albuminuria with two concomitant diseases n=40		Chronic heart failure II-III FS with albuminuria and patients with three or more concomitant diseases n=40	
		Absolute	%	Absolute	%	Absolute	%
1	Men	17	42,5	19	47,5	21	52,5
2	Women	23	57,5	21	52,5	19	47,5
3	Middle Age	58,3±4,2		61,8±4,7		65,9±5,3	
DISEASES CAUSING CHRONIC HEART FAILURE							
1	Ischemic heart disease	18	45	20	50	22	55
2	Ischemic heart disease, post-infarction cardiosclerosis	12	30	15	37,5	17	42,5
3	Hypertension	10	25	8	20	7	17,5
COMORBID DISEASES							
1	Obesity	7	17,5	8	20	8	20
2	Type II diabetes	5	12,5	6	15	7	17,5
3	Chronic pyelonephritis	7	17,5	8	20	20	50
4	Chronic gastritis	5	12,5	15	37,5	14	35
5	Irritable bowel syndrome	4	10	13	32,5	20	50
6	Remission period of chronic bronchitis	2	5	4	10	20	50
7	Remission period of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	1	2,5	7	17,5	17	42,5
8	Benign prostate adenoma	2	5	6	15	14	35
9	Anemia 1,2 degrees	5	12,5	10	25	17	42,5
10	Chronic hepatitis	2	5	3	7,5	4	10

In order to study the relationship between albuminuria and fibrosis markers and their dynamics before and after treatment, cystatin C, aldosterone, and TGF-β1 were determined using the enzyme immunoassay. Patients' resistance to physical activity was also assessed in meters, and quality of life and clinical status were assessed in points. The results were compared with albuminuria indices. Six-minute walk test, clinical

status assessment scale, and Minnesota questionnaire assessments before and after treatment of chronic heart failure with various comorbidities.

Six-minute walk test, clinical status assessment scale, and Minnesota questionnaire are widely used in scientific and applied medicine for clinical assessment of CHF treatment criteria. From this point of view, we studied the number of comorbidities in our patients before and after treatment. In case of CHF combined with one, two, three or more comorbid diseases, the six-minute walk test values before and after treatment were 391.1 ± 11.0 and 469.03 m, 335.5 ± 8.0 and 423 ± 9.3 , respectively, 276.7 ± 9.8 and 405.1 ± 12.3 m and in all cases $R < 0.001$.

Results of the 6-minute walk test before and after treatment of chronic heart failure with various comorbid diseases.

It was noted that in the first group the value increased by 78 meters, in the second group - by 88 meters and in the third group - by 12.9 meters.

According to the Minnesota questionnaire, the scores before and after treatment were 48.9 ± 2.1 and 25.5 ± 1.77 ($R < 0.001$) or 23.4 points, 55.6 ± 1.9 and $28. \pm 2.8$ respectively ($R < 0.001$) or 27.1 points improved to 58.3 ± 2.0 , 34.0 ± 7.0 ($R < 0.001$) or 24.3 points

Assessment of the quality of life before and after treatment of chronic heart failure with various comorbidities

The analysis confirms that the quality of life of patients significantly changed after three months of treatment in all groups of patients. Also, according to the clinical status assessment scale determined before and after CHF treatment, the indicators improved by 30 points - 5.4 ± 0.19 and 3.4 ± 0.23 , respectively, in the presence of one comorbid disease in the patient - 6.1 ± 0.4 and 6.1 ± 0.4 , respectively. in the presence of two comorbid conditions in the patient, the scores decreased from 4.38 ± 0.13 to 1.74 indicators, and in patients with three or more comorbid diseases, the scores decreased to 6.88 ± 0.17 and 4.56 ± 0.2 , respectively, and changed positively to 2.32 indicators. Assessment of the clinical status before and after treatment of chronic heart failure with various comorbidities. Numerical analysis shows that it has a reliable ($R < 0.05$) positive effect on the clinical condition of patients. The analysis confirmed that the resistance of patients to physical activity, quality of life and clinical status of patients changed for the better, which corresponds to the number of comorbid cases of CHF. Conclusion: When CHF is accompanied by various comorbid diseases, the resistance of patients to physical activity, clinical condition and quality of life worsen in accordance with their number. After complex treatment, physical activity increases by 88 meters when one comorbid condition is detected, by 88 and 12.9 meters when two and three comorbid conditions are present, respectively. The indicators of quality of life and clinical status changed positively, decreasing by 23.4 27.1, 24.3 and 2.0 1.72 0.2 points, respectively. Combined treatment with the addition of aldisartan and eplerenone in patients with CHF leads to a reliable decrease in markers of proteinuria and fibrosis. A high reliable result is observed when the disease is accompanied by one comorbid disease.

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